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Social Support, Self-Efficacy, and Spirituality of Adolescents: A Structural Equation Model of Their Personal Resilience During a Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The research identified the best fit model of personal resilience among 400 adolescents during a pandemic in Region XII, Philippines. A quantitative non-experimental method employing descriptive-correlation approach was utilized. The study applied mean, multiple regression, Pearson-product moment correlation, and structural equation modeling in analyzing the data. Results exhibited that the three exogenous variables, specifically, social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality, and the endogenous variable which is personal resilience were very high. The exogenous variables significantly influence the endogenous variable with spirituality as the best predictor of personal resilience. The best-fit model recognized the important connection of the three exogenous variables with personal resilience. The best fit model accentuated and established that social support, indicated by emotional support and instrumental support; self-efficacy, indicated by persistence; and spirituality, indicated by a feeling of security and mindfulness influenced and best predict the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic as indicated by novelty-seeking and emotional regulation. Nonetheless, social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality abetted adolescents to develop personal resilience to handle distress and cope during the pandemic.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, the occurrence and spread of infectious diseases called pandemics has been inevitable (Piret & Boivin, 2020). The Black Death, which originated in East Asia lasted in Europe until early 19th century and took away at least 200 million individuals and killed almost 30% of Europe's population (Wagner, et.al, 2014). On the other hand, Cholera is also considered a devastating pandemic in Asia until 1817 which first spread from India which killed millions of people (Albert, et.al, 1998). At present, the world is facing another pandemic- the Coronavirus (COVID-19). It was declared by the World Health Organization as a pandemic on March 2022 and from that point onward, it negatively affected not only people's physical health, but all other aspects of human life (Ruiz-Manriquez, et.al, 2020; Ghosh, et.al, 2020). Unfortunately, the associated social and economic stressors of the COVID-19 pandemic dented adolescents' development and well-being not only physical, but also psycho-emotional, social, intellectual, mental health, education, social relationships, and overall well-being (Bartlett & Vivrette, 2020; Chowdhury et. al., 2022; Cluver, et.al, 2020; Verguet & Jamison, 2017).

The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2020), reported that during pandemic, adolescents face not only the threat of the disease itself but also the interruption of vital services, and the increasing poverty and inequality. In the Philippines, the Asian Population and Development Association (2021), reported that adolescents are more prone to teenage pregnancy, have experience more violence at home, faced disruption in their education, experience exclusion, and mental health concerns. Further, Malaluan, Razal, Velasco & Tantengco (2022), stated that Filipino adolescents may also

experience neglect and exploitation. The National Center for Mental Health (2021), recorded a surge in suicide-related calls with 400 calls per month in 2021 versus the pre-pandemic period of 80 calls per month.

Resilience as a protective factor help individuals with positive coping skills to have lesser signs of fretfulness, anxiety, and trauma during the pandemic (Wang, et.al, (2020); Connor & Davidson, 2020). In contrast, those who are likely to fail adapting will experience lesser self-control, uneasiness, and will have difficulty to achieve goals (Azzahra, 2017). Being resilient can help adolescents cope with the pandemic (Center on Developing Child, 2020).

Moreover, new studies suggest that adolescents who are resilient are less likely to experience pressure and stress and can fulfill their dreams despite the struggles and difficulties that they may experience along the way (Fischer *et al.*, 2019; Ollmann *et al.*, 2021; Hjemdal *et al.*, 2011; Hendriani, 2018). Additionally, adolescents who showed greater resilience level are able to benefit despite uncertain circumstances, like the Covid-19 pandemic which upset their regular activities (Beames, et.al, 2021).

Theoretical ideas and empirical research indicate that social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality influences resilience. The Social support received is essential for the attainment of good physical and mental health and the promotion of resilience as it promote satisfaction and value in life by helping individuals to feel appreciated and connected with social networks and therefore acts as a protective factor (Ozbay, Johnson, Dimoulas, Morgan, Charney, & Southwick, 2017; Li, Luo, Mu, *et al.*, 2020; Camara & Padilla, 2017). Social support received by adolescents from their love ones can lower depressive symptoms and psychological distress and strengthening

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connections through the extension of relational network can increase tolerance on distresses (Ioannou, Kassianos, & Symeou, 2019 & Khatiwada, Muzembo, Wada, Ikeda, 2021).

Further, self-efficacy according to Sari, *et al* (2020), is the most important factor for adolescents' resilience during a pandemic. It is considered to be an essential element of resilience, particularly for adolescents in the face of the current pandemic because it promote coping for adolescents and is vital for the promotion of happiness and satisfaction (Walsh, *et al.*, 2020); Cuartero & Tur, 2021; Sari, *et. al.*, 2020; Banerjee, 2020). Additionally, spirituality is perceived as an important factor that can help adolescents overcome the negative effects and impact of the pandemic, specially averting depression and hopelessness (Ozawa, *et al.*, 2017; Gray, 2017; Levin, 2020). Spirituality improves resilience among individuals who have experienced traumatic events as a way to restore meaning and reduce the development of a posttraumatic stress disorder, including that of the pandemic (Park *et al.*, 2017; Hayes *et al.*, 2017; Aten *et al.*, 2019).

In consideration to these contexts, the researcher pursued to conduct this study with three exogenous variables for adolescents' personal resilience during a pandemic namely: social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality. Insufficient research were done on the vulnerability of adolescents and the factors that enhance their resilience and overall wellbeing (Tso,*et.al*, 2020; Rome, Dinardo, & Issac, 2020).

Therefore, there is a need for research to analyze adolescents' resilience as the capacity to adapt and remain steadfast in difficult situations brought by the pandemic and be able to live life amidst vulnerability and distress (Hardiyati, *et.al*, 2022; Jiao *et al.*, 2020). The study bridged the gap on limited studies of adolescents' personal resilience as such will also be the first study on adolescents' personal resilience amidst the Covid-19 pandemic in Region XII, Philippines. Consequently, it is hoped that a model for the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic produced out of this study can help achieve the goals set forth in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (2003), which aims to safeguard respect for the right of adolescents to health and development, considering both individual behaviours and environmental factors which decreases their vulnerability and associated risks and help them develop harmoniously in a free society.

The research pursued to determine the best fit model that predicts the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic. Specifically, this study has the following objectives:

1. To assess the level of social support of adolescents in terms of:
 - 1.1 emotional support; and
 - 1.2 instrumental support
2. To determine the level of self-efficacy of adolescents in terms of:
 - 2.1 initiative;

- 2.2 effort; and
 - 2.3 persistence.
3. To gage the level of spirituality of adolescents in terms of:
 - 3.1 belief in God;
 - 3.2 search for meaning
 - 3.3 mindfulness; and
 - 3.4 feeling of security.
4. To measure the level of personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic in terms of:
 - 4.1 novelty seeking;
 - 4.2 emotional regulation; and
 - 4.3 positive future orientation.
5. To define the relationship between:
 - 5.1 social support and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic;
 - 5.2 self-efficacy and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic; and
 - 5.3 spirituality and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.
6. To define the significant influence of social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality towards the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.
7. To determine the best fit model for the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between:
 - 1.1 social support and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic;
 - 1.2 self-efficacy and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic; and
 - 1.3 spirituality and personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.
2. Social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality have no significant influence on the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.
3. There is no best fit model that predicts personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Support

Positive relationships with one's family, peers, and the society itself can positively mold man's growth directions, thereby lessening delinquency (Kort-Butler, 2017). Kort-Butler (2017) further contends that when communities provides adequate social support it decrease delinquencies among adolescents. Aside from adolescent growth, social support has vital role in the promotion of mental health and disease alleviation. Laksmita *et al.* (2020) explained that social support is sensitive and often disrupted during disasters, commotions, and crises. Consequently, it is also important to establish social support among the population during such crises, especially for adolescents – the population segment whose reliance to social support is of highest relevance. Li, *et al.* (2021) found that during

the pandemic caused by the COVID-19, which entailed strict social isolation, social support became scarce, and thus, had consequently affected the psychological wellbeing of populations across age groups.

Emotional support, the first indicator of Social support. The absence of emotional support can result in a massive decrease in interest in pursuits, leisure, social activities, feelings of worthlessness and powerlessness, depression or despair, self-consciousness, unhealthy obsession with self, and confusion, self-hatred, among other things (Aslam & Ahmed, 2019). Social connections and emotional support are valuable resources. Emotional support may act as a buffer, moderating or mediating the potential harmful impacts of catastrophes on mental health, while post-event mental health issues such as PTSD symptoms may erode support in the long run (Van Der Velden, *et al.*, 2020).

Instrumental support, the second indicator of Social support. Instrumental support, a sort of social support, is assistance offered to address concrete needs. Help with personal and medical care, transportation, and resource provision are examples of instrumental support (Schultz *et al.*, 2022). Instrumental support differs from emotional support in the sense that emotional support relates to others' care and understanding, as well as intimate interaction, whereas instrumental assistance refers to people's material or practical aids in everyday duties (Yi *et al.*, 2018). Wang (2019) points out that although emotional support and instrumental support are variations of social support, they differ in the way they affect behaviors.

Self- efficacy

A person can build a sense of self-efficacy through successfully performing a skill, observing someone else successfully completing a task, receiving positive feedback about successfully accomplishing a project, or relying on physiological signals (Zulkosky, 2019). Additionally, self and collective-efficacy growth can be protective factors against trauma, prejudice, and other stresses. Those who deal with adolescents, particularly those from racial and sexual minority groups, should help them develop self-efficacy in order to create resilience (Sedillo-Hamann, 2021). Moreover, decline in adolescent motivation can be prevented by fostering self-efficacy and positive sensations through instructional practices that promote the healthy accomplishment objectives (Schweder, 2020). Initiative, the first indicator of Self-efficacy.

According to Lisbona *et al.* (2018) demonstrate strong correlations of self-efficacy to wellbeing by identifying it to be a generator of well-being and a beneficial resource for dealing with job demands by functioning as a stress buffer. In context to the current plague, Kapila *et al.* (2020) contend that in order to protect learning, institutions must continue to encourage self-initiative while also developing innovative ways of providing education to learning adolescents. According to Lee, *et al.* (2019), flipped learning has a beneficial impact on boosting students' self-directed (via self-initiative) learning capabilities, and the

results differ depending on the sorts of teaching methods used. In terms of population coverage, education systems are expanding, with the youth continuing their education at the vocational and higher levels.

Persistence, the second indicator of Self-efficacy. The empirical investigations illustrates how optimism influences an individual to cope with unperfected situations (Niemiec 2019). Mostly of individual researches identified these qualities in the field of positive psychology that helped a person overcome challenges (Peterson and Seligman, 2004). Individual traits such as persistence and personal characteristics are essential to well-being and life pleasure, but they may be more crucial in times of difficulty. They may thus play an important role in a pandemic lockdown as well (Casali, *et al.*, 2021). Effort, the third indicator of Self-efficacy.

The spread of coronavirus illness (COVID-19) and the associated countermeasures can have a substantial influence on teenage well-being. Longitudinal studies that give insight on prospective social, emotional, and behavioral development in teenagers are lacking (Daniunaite *et al.*, 2021). Effective perspectives foster intrinsic interest and thorough immersion in activities. They set high expectations for themselves and stick to them tenaciously. When they fail, they intensify and continue their attempts (Bandura, 1994). As a matter of fact Lovu, *et al.* (2015) suggest that effort may be considerably predicted by both attitude and self-efficacy. It was discovered that attitude did not predict academic accomplishment when a second multiple regression analysis was done to count the prediction weight of attitude, self-efficacy, and effort.

Spirituality

Spiritually oriented attitudes have been linked to greater psychologically and physically stress tolerance, healthy maturity, and improved capacity in overcoming with severe illness and solitude (Taylor & Francis, 2020). Religion and spirituality are therefore crucial in everyday life. Spirituality may improve both psychological and physical health. The aptitude to recover from or cope with adversity is referred to as resilience. Spiritual and religious beliefs may be linked to critical "resilience assets" (Schwalm *et al.*, 2021; Hardy, *et al.* (2019) suggest that first, religiosity/spirituality is often protective to teenagers, shielding them from unfavorable consequences and encouraging healthy youth development and thriving Belief in God, the first indicator of spirituality. Adolescence is the most sensitive phase in the development of spiritual beliefs since it is a period of awareness and searching for reinforcement of ideas. Spiritual activities, as a vital component of mental health, shape their personality and identity (Pour, 2021). Furthermore, Torralba, *et al.* (2021), stated that adolescence is usually seen as a difficult time. Positively, spiritual self-care is acknowledged as a type of self-care in which a person uses his or her spirituality, principles, and encounters to gain control over distress and problems and cope with challenges (Pirutinsky, *et al.*,

2020).

Search for meaning, the second indicator of spirituality. According to Skrzypiński (2021), spiritual intelligence, at the proper level of self-consciousness and knowledge, may help people find meaning in their lives and achieve complicated spiritual goals. In fact, Arrieira *et al.* (2018) noted in the context of medicine that spiritually-related practices, such as prayer and delivering comprehensive care, were useful therapeutic tools for offering pleasure, life with dignity, and humanization of death, in addition to assisting in understanding the end-of-life process and searching for meaning in the suffering caused by illness. Spirituality has increased life quality and decreased the risk of sickness and death (Balducci, 2018).

Mindfulness, the third indicator of Spirituality. Mindfulness is defined as the awareness and acceptance of one's own present. Although mindfulness may allow people to suffer fewer unpleasant symptoms and anxiety during the COVID-19 epidemic, given the particular circumstances of individuals and the various challenges linked with the disease, it may not alter individual anxiety (Dehgan *et al.*, 2021). Munif *et al.*, (2019) discovered that respondents (intervention and control groups) had significantly different levels of stress

Feeling of security, the fourth indicator of Spirituality. Security implies a sense of harmony with nature as well as a firm conviction in spirituality. This sense of security can be understood by the strong bonds that exist between humans and nature (Moufakkir & Nouredine, 2017). Even in the most terrible of situations, spiritual security may bring a sense of calm and protection. Indeed, for some, the more severe the situation, the more important this aspect of security becomes (Fisher & Leonardi, 2020).

Adolescent Resilience

Individual and societal resilience is outlined as the ability to navigate to and strive against external and internal forces. In times of stress, it can safeguard people's well-being and growth. As a result, resilience is dependent on both individual traits and the resources supplied by a supportive environment (Holtge *et al.*, 2021). Dvorsky *et al.* (2021) suggest that during the COVID-19 crisis, intrinsic curiosity and a positive mindset may be especially essential for developing resilience. Pecjak *et al.* (2021) hold that because to the COVID-19 epidemic, adolescents' social and learning experiences have been drastically altered by distant learning and social isolation, thereby affecting their resiliency. Their research discovered a link between resilience and adolescents' psychological well-being. More resilient adolescents report less discomfort and more support than less resilient students, and resilience, coupled with social support, has been proven to intervene between the stressful COVID-19 setting and acute stress disorders. Families, friends, schools, and communities all have a role in the development of resiliency (Dvorsky *et al.*, 2020).

Novelty seeking, the first indicator of Adolescent

resilience. According to Gineikiene *et al.* (2022), novelty seeking as a wide and domain-general inclination to be drawn to and choose new and unfamiliar feelings and experiences. According to Hodges *et al.* (2018), adolescence is a crucial stage of social behavior development that can be disturbed by stresses. Adolescents with a high level of novelty seeking may be more resilient to the impacts of social pressures. However, in the study of Manetsch (2022), it was found that novelty seeking predicted temperament and offending behavior recidivism among adolescents.

Emotional regulation, the second indicator of adolescent resilience. According to Green *et al.* (2021), the COVID-19 epidemic threatens adolescence, a vital stage for socio-emotional development. Emotional responsiveness is a person's emotional response to an event or shift the environment. Persons with higher emotional reactivity are likely to be receptive to their environment and its effects (Green *et al.*, 2021). In addition, adolescence is marked by unstable emotion as it also increase the number and degree of their emotion reaction, especially during adolescence where unstable emotion is common (Orben, *et al.*, 2020).

Positive future orientation, the third indicator of Adolescent resilience. In the context of adolescent resilience, Masten & Barnes (2018), stipulated that it is focused on evaluating the experience of those who were raised in detrimental environments yet were able to achieve a quality life. Moreover, according to recent researches, having a sense of purpose and meaning promotes adolescent resilience and finding a passion and purpose is therefore a vital method for teens and young people to boost their resilience, even in difficult circumstances, and recover more rapidly when life knocks them down (Sagone, *et al.*, 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The research made use of quantitative non-experimental design using descriptive and correlational techniques. This was employed to apply theories, mathematical models, and/or hypothesis regarding an event. Structural Equation modelling was used to identify the best fit model. Firstly, it employed the descriptive correlational method which describes a particular trait, aspect, or feature of a group with continuous data response and depicts an average level means (Gill, 2013), Correlation was employed to examine and quantify the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational research according to Creswell (2012), is a type of quantitative non-experimental design in research that measure, describe, and establish the relationship of variables using correlational type of statistics. Structural equation modelling was used in this study that put efforts to generate the best fit model on personal resilience that may aid in strengthening and enhancing the resilience of adolescents during difficult time, specifically during pandemic. The multiple dependence relationships among

variables at the same time was given emphasis, hence a multivariate technique (Bose, 2019). Specifically, the research study investigated the relationship of social support, self-efficacy, spirituality, and personal resilience among adolescents. When taken side by side with different variations of statistical methods, the structural equation model proves more complicated in analyzing data. As a tool, it is often utilized to delineate causal conclusions from a pool of data which can be observed and assumptions which are largely theoretical (Bhatta, Albert, Kahana & Lekhak, 2017; Hair, Babin, & Krey, 2017; Pearl, 2012). The normal theory method was also used in the study especially on parameter estimates since a large sample is needed to have an impartial, efficient, and consistent convergence for sample (Tomarken, 2005). Hence, in determining the best fit model, some adjustments were done in data fitting like exclusions of indicators that have low values towards one variable- endogenous.

Research Locale

This research was conducted in Region 12, a region in the Philippines located in South-Central Mindanao. South and North Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, and the Sarangani Province, are its four provinces. The researcher took the decision to have the study among the adolescents within Region XII, Philippines, because he wanted to find out in a broader scope whether self-efficacy, social support, and spirituality correlate and influence the personal resilience of adolescents amidst a pandemic. The Coronavirus 19 pandemic affected the region as shown in the data presented by the different provincial COVID tracker. Thus, conducting this study in the region can scientifically identify the level of social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality of adolescents and personal resilience as dependent and independent variables respectively. This will be the first multivariate study to be conducted in the region with the application of Structural Equation Modelling. Moreover, the region is highly accessible to the researcher, thus convenient on his part to gather data which were highly needed to attain the purpose of the study.

Population and Sample

A science-driven method was utilized to choose the respondents of this study. To identify the population of adolescents within the region, the data was obtained from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) and the Local Government Units of the identified cities with adolescent populations in order to compile thorough lists of adolescents in each locales. The aforementioned inventory were utilized to determine the quantity of adolescents in the 12th Region who may potentially be identified as respondents. The researcher used convenient sampling to gather the needed data from the 400 adolescents from four Cities. Collection of data was done from September 2021 to November 2021. Convenience sampling is a type of purposeful sampling which aims to use the researcher's personal judgment based on the prescribed and identified

characteristics of respondents and place of the central phenomenon with the respondents readily available (Creswell, 2012.). Moreover, having a sample of more than 200 is ideal because it reduce errors of measurement when doing Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) as it necessitates huge sample (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012; Hair, et.al, 2016). Thus, obtaining a sample size of 400 is both justifiable and suitable. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child explains adolescence as “the period between 10 and 19 years of age” (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, 1986). In this study adolescents between 15-19 years old were considered as the respondents since they are one of the most vulnerable group during the pandemic based on related studies and this age bracket of adolescents are the most accessible during the pandemic because they can access the internet and can manipulate computers and other gadgets. They must have resided in Region XII for at least one (1) year prior to the conduct of the study. Must be enrolled in an academic institution. The potential research respondent who lack any of the above – stated qualifications subject for inclusion were excluded from the participating in the study like: aged below 15 years old, resided in the region less than one (1) year, not enrolled in an academic institution. Adolescents who are not enrolled in an academic institution during the conduct of the study are excluded since they are difficult to reach out during the pandemic. Respondents may withdraw at any time if they are uncomfortable, afraid, or there is a real or apparent harm to their bodily, mental, or emotional regard of security. Respondents who will withdraw from the survey will be allowed and will be replaced by an equally qualified respondent with the same age, sex, and location.

Research Instrument

The study utilized the gathering of primary data about the constructs which include social support, self-efficacy, spirituality, and personal resilience of adolescents. The survey questionnaires used were collected from many relevant studies, with some alterations and contextualization to meet the study's respondents. The data gathering tool was reframed to suit the existing context. The said research tool has a Filipino translation for efficient gathering of data. The instrument was verified by six specialists in the field of social development to assess its suitability, and it received a general rate of 4.38 which translates to “very good.” A pilot testing was carried out following the approval. Cronbach alpha was employed so as to assess the data gathering material's reliability, yielding the forth running alpha coefficient results: social support (.920), self-efficacy (.835), spirituality (.834), and personal resilience (.807). The Cronbach alpha consistency coefficient typically arrays from zero to one (Collins, 2007s). The coefficient, however, had a limit. The nearer the Cronbach alpha's coefficient to one, the greater the internal reliability of the items in the scale (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). Moreover, Darren and Mallery

(1999) claimed the rule of thumb in measuring the questionnaire's consistency using Cronbach's alpha: if the result is larger than or equal to 0.9 it is excellent; larger than or equal to 0.8 is good; larger than or equal to 0.7 is acceptable; larger than or equal to 0.6 is questionable; larger than or equal to 0.5 is poor; and larger than or equal to 0.4 is undesirable.

The survey on social support was derived from Schwarzer & Schulz (2013). The said instrument is crafted to measure the social support received by the adolescents grounded on two factors, namely: emotional support, and instrumental support. The feedback of the research informants were analyzed through the following scale: The survey instrument for self-efficacy was adapted from

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The measures on social support are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The measures on social support are often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The measures on social support are sometimes observed
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The measures on social support are seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The measures on social support never observed

the study of Bosscher & Smit (1997). The instrument is outlined to measure the self-efficacy of adolescents based on three components, specifically: initiative, effort, and

persistence. Feedback of the research informants was analyzed through the scale: The survey instrument for spirituality was inspired by

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The measures on self-efficacy are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The measures on self-efficacy are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The measures on self-efficacy are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The measures on self-efficacy are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The measures on self-efficacy are never manifested.

the research of Hardt, et.al (2012). The research tool is structured to quantify the spirituality of adolescents based on four factors, namely: belief in God, search for

meaning, mindfulness, and feeling of security. Responses of the study participants were interpreted using the scale: The survey instrument for adolescent resilience was

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The measures on spirituality are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The measures on spirituality are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The measures on spirituality are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The measures on spirituality are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The measures on spirituality are never manifested.

adapted from the study of Oshio, et.al (2003). The instrument is designed to measure the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic based on three

factors, namely: novelty seeking, emotional regulation, and positive future orientation. Responses of the study participants were interpreted using the scale:

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The measures on personal resilience are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The measures on personal resilience are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The measures on personal resilience are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The measures on personal resilience are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The measures on personal resilience are never manifested.

Data Collection

Multiple steps were completed to acquire the information required for the research. The initial step was to obtain approval to conduct the research, of which was obtained from the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) on September 23, 2021. The researcher then visited offices of various local government mayors in Region XII (SOCCSKSARGEN) in pursuit of obtaining permission to perform the study. Upon its approval, the preparation of Google Form to serve as survey questionnaire was facilitated from September to October 2021. Authorized letters of request verified

under the scrutiny of the adviser and the dean of the graduate school were disseminated through Google Form to the selected adolescents in the SOCCSKSARGEN region, together with the questionnaires. Then, from October to January 2021, a timetable for the floating and retrieval of questionnaires was created. Continuous management and collection of data and tabulation were carried out, with information screening performed to identify outliers during the analysis. Finally, data analysis and interpretation from 400 respondents, in which the results were evaluated and interpreted to give significance to the study.

Statistical Treatment

Data accumulated through the questionnaires were subjected to tallying and treatment with the use of the following tools on statistics:

Mean

This was utilized to identify the degree interpersonal support, spirituality, self-efficacy, and resilience of adolescents.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation

This was utilized to build the important link concerning interpersonal support, spirituality, self-efficacy, and resilience of adolescents.

Multiple Regression

This was utilized in identifying vital determinants of adolescent resilience.

Structural Equation Modelling

The research mandated the employment of SEM in discovering the best-fit-model. The core of the test based on Savalel and Bentler (2010) has been to confirm the exclusion of the elements with low relationship to the elements of the other latent factors in final SEM.

RESULTS

Level of Social Support of Adolescents during Pandemic Presented in table 1 is the level of social support adolescents receive. The mean overall score received by social support is 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.48, described as very high. This means that social support is always observed. Specifically, the mean rating of the indicators of social support are tell as follows: emotional support obtained a mean rating of 4.59 or very high; instrumental support attained a mean rating of 4.19 or high. The overall very high response of the adolescents

Table 1: Level of Social Support of Adolescents

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional Support	0.51	4.32	Very High
Instrumental Support	0.61	4.19	High
Overall	0.48	4.25	Very High

means that the domain of social support are observed most of the time.

Level of Self-efficacy of Adolescents during Pandemic

Shown in Table 2 is the summary of self-efficacy of

adolescents. The overall mean score received by self-efficacy is 4.23 with a standard deviation of 0.48, described as very high. This means that self-efficacy is always manifested by the adolescents. Specifically, the mean rating of the indicators of self-efficacy are reveal as

Table 2: Level of Self-efficacy of Adolescents

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Initiative	0.58	4.20	Very High
Effort	0.54	4.25	Very High
Persistence	0.64	4.26	Very High
Overall	0.48	4.23	Very High

follows: initiative obtained a mean rating of 4.20 or very high; effort attained a mean rating of 4.25 or very high; and persistence got a mean rating of 4.26 or very high.

Level of Self-efficacy of Adolescents during Pandemic

Table 3 displays the results on the level of spirituality

of the adolescents. The overall mean rating is 4.42 with a standard deviation of 0.40, described as very high, which means that spirituality is always manifested by the respondents during a pandemic. The mean score of the indicators of spirituality are conveyed as follows: belief in God earned a mean of 4.73 or very high; search for

Table 3: Level of Spirituality of Adolescents

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Belief in God	0.51	4.73	Very High
Search for Meaning	0.60	4.32	Very High
Mindfulness	0.44	4.35	Very High
Feeling of Security	0.65	4.27	Very High
Overall	0.40	4.42	Very High

meaning garnered a mean rating of 4.32 or very high; mindfulness has a mean rating of 4.35 or very high; and feeling of security got a mean rating of 4.27 or very high.

Level of Personal Resilience of Adolescents

Showed in Table 4 is the level of personal resilience of adolescents in Region XII. The overall mean score is 4.38 with a standard deviation of 0.44, described as very high

which means that personal resilience is always manifested by the respondents during a pandemic. The mean rating of the indicators of personal resilience are elaborated as follows: novelty seeking obtained a mean rating of 4.19 or high; emotional regulation has a mean rating of 4.29 or very high; and positive future orientation attained a mean rating of 4.66 or very high.

Table 4: Level of Personal Resilience of Adolescents

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Novelty Seeking	0.57	4.19	High
Emotional Regulation	0.65	4.29	Very High
Positive Future Orientation	0.44	4.66	Very High
Overall	0.44	4.38	Very High

Significance on the Relationship between Social Support and Personal Resilience

Table 5 shows the data on the results of significance on the relationship between social support and personal resilience of adolescents in region XII. The overall r- value attained by the said measures is 0.471. The p-value is higher than 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. Additionally, it is seen that emotional support

and instrumental support as variables of social support when correlated to novelty seeking, the overall r- value is 0.408 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. When the indicators of social support are correlated to emotional regulation, the overall r- value is 0.357 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Moreover, when the social support indicators are correlated to positive future orientation, it has an overall r- value is 0.366 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant.

Table 5: Significance on the Relationship between Social Support and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Personal Resilience				
Social Support	Novelty Seeking	Emotional Regulation	Positive Future Orientation	Overall
Emotional Support	.248** .000	.206** .000	.287** .000	.302** .000
Instrumental Support	.436** .000	.390** .000	.337** .000	.490** .000
Overall	.408** .000	.357** .000	.366** .000	.471** .000

* $p < .05$

Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Table 6 displays the data on the results of significance on the relationship between self-efficacy and personal resilience. The overall r-value obtained from the aforementioned measures is 0.638 with a p-value of less than 0.05 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. The result is significant, and the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. Furthermore, when the indicators of self-efficacy namely: initiative, effort, and persistence were correlated with the novelty seeking, the r- value was .596 with a p-value of less than 0.05 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. The result entails that it is significant. Additionally, the indicators of self-efficacy when correlated with emotional

regulation revealed an r- value of .515 with $p < 0.05$ thus, significant. However, when the indicator of self-efficacy: persistence when correlated with positive future orientation, garnered an r- value of .391, with $p < 0.05$, thus, significant. Hence, rejects the null hypothesis. The overall result between self-efficacy and personal resilience is found to be significant. Thus, it rejects the null hypothesis.

Significance on the Relationship between Spirituality and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Table 7 shows the data on the results of significance on the relationship between spirituality and personal resilience. The overall r- value is 0.736 with $p < 0.05$ which is significant rejecting the null hypothesis of no

Table 6: Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Personal Resilience				
Self-efficacy	Novelty Seeking	Emotional Regulation	Positive Future Orientation	Overall
Initiative	.524** .000	.441** .000	.281** .000	.535** .000
Effort	.456** .000	.350** .000	.285** .000	.461** .000
Persistence	.486** .000	.466** .000	.387** .000	.565** .000
Overall	.596** .000	.515** .000	.391** .000	.638** .000

* $p < .05$

significant relationship. Additionally, it is observed that belief in God, search for meaning, mindfulness, and feeling of security as indicators of spirituality when correlated to novelty seeking, the overall r- value is 0.636 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Likewise, when indicators of spirituality are correlated to emotional regulation, the

overall r- value is 0.606 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Moreover, when indicators of spirituality are correlated to positive future orientation, the overall r- value is 0.502 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. The probability values showed significant correlations.

Table 7: Significance on the Relationship between Spirituality and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Personal Resilience				
Self-efficacy	Novelty Seeking	Emotional Regulation	Positive Future Orientation	Overall
Belief in God	.162** .001	.186** .000	.423** .000	.299** .000
Search for Meaning	.555** .000	.395** .000	.409** .000	.566** .000
Mindfulness	.600** .000	.643** .000	.438** .000	.717** .000
Feeling of Security	.527** .000	.562** .000	.237** .000	.580** .000
Overall	.636** .000	.608** .000	.502** .000	.736** .000

* $p < .05$

Significance on the Influence of Social Support, Self-efficacy, and Spirituality on the Personal Resilience of Adolescents in Region XII during a Pandemic

Presented in Table 8 is the results of regression analysis showing the significant influence of exogenous variables: social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality on personal resilience. The result revealed that the three exogenous variables are found to be significant predictor of personal resilience having an F- value of 204.108 with a p- value less than 0.05.

The analysis reveals that when social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality are regressed with personal resilience, it generates a computed R2 value or coefficient of determination value of 0.607, meaning 60.70 percent

of the variance of personal resilience is attributed to social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality. This means that 39.30 percent of the variation can be attributed to other variables not covered in the study. As revealed in the F-value of 204.108 ($p < 0.01$). Social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality influenced personal resilience. The result is significant hence the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected. Moreover, on a singular capacity of the independent variables- social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality significantly influence the personal resilience of adolescents during the pandemic with their p- values < 0.05 . Of the three variables, spirituality was noted to be the best predictor of personal resilience based on the beta standardized coefficients.

Table 8: Significance on the Relationship between Spirituality and Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Personal Resilience				
Exogenous Variables	B	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.402		2.429	.016
Social Support	.050	.054	1.399	.163
Self-efficacy	.270	.293	7.102	.000
Spirituality	.594	.537	13.218	.000
R	.779			
R2	.607			
ΔR	.604			
F	204.108			
q	.000			

Establishing the Best Fit Model for Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

This portion highlights the analysis on the interrelationships among social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality to the personal resilience of adolescents in Region XII during the pandemic. There are five

alternative models tested to achieve the best fit model of personal resilience of adolescents. Every model produced a framework that could be split into two sub-models, which are measurements of loads on each factor to its latent construct, while the structural model describes the relationships between the latent variables. Furthermore, the assessment of fit is utilized to decide whether to accept or reject the model. In general, the researcher established the causation link of the latent variable towards the other latent variables. Furthermore, it establishes the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables. When the structural model demonstrates a suitable fit, it indicates

that the actual connections among variables indicated by the model are consistent. The amount and direction of the association between variables are estimated by the model parameters. Variable screening was meticulously monitored to place a premium on the data's normalcy. In the model formulation, variables having interval or ratio data are tallied. This study's generated model is supported by theories.

There are five generated models presented in the study. The summary of the findings of the goodness of fit measures of these five generated models is presented in table 9 above. In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must consistently fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/ degrees of freedom value should be less than 5 with its corresponding p-value result of greater than 0.05. Root-mean square error (RMSEA)

approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding P-close value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as the normed-fit- index (NFI), Tucker- Lewis index (TLI), comparative-fit index (CFI) and the goodness of fit- index (GFI) must all be greater than 0.95.

The table shows that Model 5 have indices that consistently indicate a very good fit to the data as all the indices presented fall within each criterion. Moreover, the model fitting was calculated as being highly acceptable as presented in table 9. The Chi-square divided by the degrees of freedom was 1.745 with the P-value of .065. This indicated a very good fit model to the data. This was also strongly supported by RMSEA index of .043 which was less than to 0.05 level of significance with its corresponding P-close value is greater than 0.05.

Table 9: Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMINDF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSE (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	6.148	.889	.869	.849	.831	.114	.000
2	.000	6.319	.891	.870	.851	.825	.115	.000
3	.000	6.204	.891	.870	.850	.829	.114	.000
4	.000	7.000	.877	.850	.831	.803	.123	.000
5	.065	1.745	.987	.993	.984	.986	.043	.587

Legend: CMIN/DF – Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom, NFI–Normed Fit Index, GFI– Goodness of Fit Index, TLI–Tucker-Lewis Index, RMSEA– Root Mean Square of Error Approximation, CFI–Comparative Fit Index

Likewise, the other indices such as NFI, TLI and CFI were found to be consistently indicating a very good fit model as their values, all fall within each criterion. Thus, there was no need to find another model for testing because it was already found to be the best fit among all the tested model.

Therefore, the null hypothesis of no best fit model

was rejected. It could be stated that there is a best fit model that predicts the resilience of adolescents during a pandemic in Region XII. Moreover, the model clearly illustrates the importance of social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality as a predictor of personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic. It could be perceived from the model that all two indicators of social support,

Figure 3: The Interrelationship between Social Support, Self-efficacy, and Spirituality and their Direct Causal Relationship towards Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Legend: EMS- Emotional Support, MIN- Mindfulness, INS- Instrumental Support, NOS- Novelty Seeking, PER- Persistence, EMR- Emotional Regulation, FOS- Feeling of Security

remained as significant predictor of personal resilience to wit: emotional support and instrumental support. For self-efficacy, only one out of three indicators were found to influence personal resilience namely: Persistence.

For spirituality, only two out of three indicators remained as significant predictor of personal resilience: mindfulness and feeling of security. On the part of personal resilience, only two out of three indicators remained to be measured these are novelty seeking and emotional regulation. Thus, the findings suggest that the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic is best anchored on: social support which include emotional support and instrumental support; self-efficacy which embraces persistence; and spirituality which is measured in terms of mindfulness and feeling of security, and personal resilience which was measured in terms of novelty seeking and emotional regulation.

DISCUSSION

Social Support

A Significantly high level of social support serves as the outcome of the evaluation regarding the variable's measurement namely emotional support and instrumental support that garnered very high and high ratings respectively, hence, "always observed". Significant individuals who provide social support like family and friends in the life of adolescent plays a vital role to decrease the risk of stress, increase their satisfaction, and be able to expand social relationships to lessen the effects of distress (Khatiwada, Muzembo, Wada, Ikeda, 2021).

Self-efficacy

The significant level of self-efficacy serves as the outcome of respondents' evaluation on the variable's measurement namely: initiative, effort, and persistence which all got very high results, hence "always manifested". It confirms the study of Cattellino *et al.*, (2019), that adolescents can better manage their activities and can motivate them to get over the demands of life in everyday context when they improve their agency that eventually develop self-efficacy behavior and perspectives.

Spirituality

The generally significant level of spirituality serves as the evaluation of the ratings the respondents regarding the variable's measurement, specifically: belief in God, search for meaning, mindfulness, and feeling of security that all acquired very high ratings, hence, "always manifested". It is considered a particularly important aspect since it is related to coping and the management of stressful events to maintain meaning, purpose, and connection in the face of difficult situations (Clark & Hunter, 2019).

Personal Resilience

The overall very high level of personal resilience is the outcome of the ratings of the respondents on the variable measurement namely novelty seeking, emotional regulation, and positive future orientation. All of these

measure of variable's construct got very high ratings, hence, "always manifested". This supports the research of Beames, et.al. (2021) who discovered that adolescents who showed significant levels of resiliency were capable of withstanding unprecedented scenarios, like the covid-19 pandemic that severely disrupted their daily routine.

Significance on the Relationship between Social Support and Personal Resilience

The variable relationship test shows that there is a positive association between social support and personal resilience since the overall result of social support is significantly correlated with adolescent resilience. The result of the study support the study of Ozbay, Johnson, Dimoulas, Morgan, Charney, & Southwick (2017) & Li, Luo, Mu, *et al.*, (2020), that positive social support is essential for the attainment of good physical and mental health and the promotion of resilience. Consequently, when adolescents feel that strong positive social support is available and is provided consistently they can build resilience to cope with challenges and strains, especially during the pandemic and be able to build a strong foundation for well-being throughout life.

Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy and Personal Resilience

The examination of results between variables shows that the self-efficacy of adolescents in region XII is positively correlated with personal resilience. The result of the study relates to the study conducted by Walsh, et al., (2020) and Cuartero & Tur, (2021) that self-efficacy is a component of resilience and increasing it can augment resilient behavior. This denotes that, having a strong self-efficacy encourages and build a substantial sense of resilience that ensures the probability that a person can achieved his goals in life and surpass the challenges that he may face along the way, like the pandemic.

Significance on the Relationship between Spirituality and Personal Resilience

The examination of the relationship between variables that the spirituality of adolescents is positively correlated with personal resilience. The study conducted by Gray (2017) & Levin (2020) emphasized that faith and spirituality can be perceived as a source of resilience from physical, psychological, and mental point of view, including that of the pandemic. Thus, developing high sense of spirituality among adolescents enable them to develop positive behaviors, mindset, and emotions that are essential in coping with everyday stress and help them realize their potentials as adults.

Multiple Regression Analysis on the Influence of Social Support, Self-efficacy, and Spirituality on the Personal Resilience

The R2 value or coefficient of determination value shows that the combined exogenous variables namely

social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality has 60.70% influence on the endogenous variable and 39.30 % come from other factors that are not covered by this study. Consequently, based on the regression analyses, all of three exogenous variables are found to have strong influence with personal resilience having a p -value of < 0.05 . In the singular capacities of the independent variables, it showed that all of these variables, specifically social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality (the best predictor) significantly influence the dependent variable of personal resilience. The three independent variables need each other to significantly influence the dependent variable. The result can be supported by the resiliency theory that provides a useful framework for considering how promotive factors may operate for encouraging positive youth development (Fergus & Zimmerman, 2005). The proposition of Cutrona, & Russell (1990) supports the influence of social support (emotional support and instrumental support) on personal resilience. Also Sari, *et al* (2020), connection between self-efficacy and personal resilience by stating that the self-efficacy ranks first in the phase of building resilience to adolescent students in the face of the covid-19 pandemic including initiative, effort, and persistence among others. The study of Gray (2017) & Levin (2020) emphasized that spirituality is a foundation of resilience from physical, psychological, and mental point of view.

The Best Fit Model that Predicts Personal Resilience of Adolescents during a Pandemic

Among the five hypothesized models, it was hypothesized model 5 found to satisfy the criteria for the best fit model. It shows direct causal link of the exogenous variables (social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality) on the endogenous variable, which is personal resilience. The exogenous variables are: social support with emotional support (EMS) and instrumental support (INS) as its measures; Self-efficacy which is measure by persistence (PER); and spirituality, measured in terms mindfulness (MIN) and feeling of security (FOS). It can be seen from the model that out the three indicators, only novelty seeking (NOS) and emotional regulation (EMR) persisted as the measurement of personal resilience. Novelty seeking is concerned with people's propensity to explore novel and new experiences and environments (Arenas & Manzanedo, 2017; Gocłowska *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, Artuch-Garde *et al.* (2017), mentioned that to self-regulate behavior is associated with high levels of resilience in high-school students.

For social support, as an exogenous element in the model of best fit, both the indicators appeared to have causal relationship to personal resilience. These are emotional support and instrumental support. This is coherent with the study of Burleson (2003), that receiving emotional support helps individuals, adolescents in particular, to cope with problems, anxiety, and disappointments of hope and pain in their lives and ensure a good level of psychological growth, good human interaction and

close personal relationships such as friends, family, or emotional relationships. On the other hand, instrumental support that include feelings of warmth and closeness with parents (Russek and Schwartz, 1997) and parental academic involvement (Westerlund *et al.*, 2013). Giving adolescents adequate and consistent social support under emotional and instrumental areas is beneficial for developing resilient behavior to cope with vulnerabilities. For Self-efficacy, the remaining indicator is persistence. The result supports the study of Aspinwall & Richter (1999), that specified that greater persistence and successful adaptation to stress; such beliefs may be an important aspect in the development of competence in resilient adolescents. Hence, developing self-efficacy is vital to develop resilience among adolescents and be able to achieve their goals in life.

Further, on the spirituality context of the research, mindfulness and feeling of security remain as its indicators. Faith might allow religious group members to develop and maintain a sense of meaning and feeling of security in their lives and thus enhance well-being (Schieman *et al.* 2010). Further, having life meaning and feeling of spirituality can permeate all aspects of life, facilitating the development of worldviews and offering a greater sense of purpose, meaning, joy, and security in life (Richards & Bergin, 2005). Hence, having strong spiritual core is necessary for the development of resilience despite challenging situations.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of structural equation model strengthened the consistency and reliability of the study because the analysis goes through the steps of model specification, model estimation, and model evaluation. Results showed that the level of social support, self-efficacy, spirituality, and personal resilience are very high indicating that these variables are observed and manifested by the adolescents during the pandemic. There exist important correlations of the following variants namely: social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality with personal resilience. It was found out that among the variables studied, spirituality is the most influential to the personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic in Region 12, Philippines. Model five had the indicators that consistently demonstrated a significant fit to the data among the five studied structural models; hence, it is recognized as the best fit model.

This supports the resiliency theory that provides a useful framework for considering how promotive factors may operate for encouraging positive youth development (Fergus & Zimmerman, 2005). The theory also explains why some youth grow up to be healthy adults in spite of risks exposure (Garmezy, 1991; Masten, Cutuli, Herbers, & Reed, 2007; Werner, 1982) by examining both single risks and promotive factors and the cumulative effects of multiple promotive factors across ecological domains (e.g., individual, family, community) to more accurately reflect the complex nature of influences on adolescent

development (Ostaszewski & Zimmerman, 2006; Stoddard *et al.*, 2012). As discussed by Höltinge, et. al. (2021), resilience is a complex construct resulting from a dynamic relationship between risk and protection factors in which individuals may use personal and contextual resources to overcome adversities. Further, resilience is a contributing factor in individuals' ability to adapt to stressful environments, develop effective coping strategies and improve wellbeing (Cleary *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, Hendriani, (2018) stated that people who have the ability to be resilient, was able to face a variety of pressures and difficulties that cause stress to be able to achieve the standard of living that is desired, either against the barriers that specific are at the stage of development of the particular and the whole range of life.

RECOMMENDATION

The significant relationship of the three variables: social support, self-efficacy, and spirituality towards personal resilience proves that these variables should be given sufficient considerations by the adolescents, supported by their family, friends, community and other significant individuals because when these variables are promoted and sustained, the higher is the level of personal resilience of adolescents, especially during pandemic. This can be done by providing a strong and consistent social support, develop self-efficacy, and strengthen the spirituality of adolescents that will serve as protective factors beneficial for the promotion and development of resilience amidst vulnerable situations and distress which is hoped to transcend to holistic well-being, happiness, and satisfaction.

The best fit model emphasizing social support with elements of emotional support and instrumental support; self-efficacy with persistence as indicator; and spirituality which includes mindfulness and feeling of security as enduring indicators and significant determinants of personal resilience proves that such can be the prime focus that influence personal resilience compared to other variables not included in the study. This can be done by providing adolescents adequate and constant care, love, affection, and attention. Further, establishing open communication in the context of a healthy, friendly and safe environment at home and in the community that will empower them to establish social support system, cultivate their self-efficacy, and fortify spirituality in order for them to improve and develop personal resilience to cope with adversity and distress; and succeed despite being vulnerable in the face of the pandemic and help them realize their potentials as adults.

Concerned Government instrumentalities such as the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), may formulate policy for creating enabling environment for the practice of Personal Resilience Model for it to be successful.

A study on the indicators excluded after the Structural Equation Modelling must be done to explore the characteristics of those indicators which can also be

used to ascertain the resilience of adolescents during a pandemic. Identical researches should be conducted to identify strong predictors that were not been covered by this study of personal resilience of adolescents during a pandemic. Since only one good fit model was produced, it is highly recommended to produce two or more models that may be fit to the same covariance matrix.

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